

KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION AND INFORMATION DISSEMINATION: CHALLENGES FACED BY NEW AND UPCOMING RESEARCHERS

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Abstract

Knowledge production means the gathering of related activities in the university that has to do with producing new knowledge. The emerging researchers find it so hard and difficult to engage in scientific and contribute to knowledge production because of lack of know how. Therefore, it is fundamentally importance, that the emerging researchers are made aware of the challenges that they will experience in the research process. It is not only the responsibility of researchers to produce knowledge, respondents in any research undertaken also make a greater contribution. That is why it is important that those in public sector understand the role that they play in research. Without their inputs this kinds of research would not be a success. This is a scientific way of contributing to the body of knowledge by academic staff and students. The academic community is continually conversing about knowledge and the many forms it takes, as well as ways of thinking about how to organise and arrange knowledge into categories, such as disciplines. This paper focuses on the challenges upcoming or first-time researchers experience when researching in order to make contribution into the body of knowledge. However, there are obstacles in the process that impede progress, making it impossible to produce knowledge and disseminate information to the communities. Therefore, this paper also discusses the process of knowledge production in the context of research, data collection, sampling challenges, arranging for interviews, fatigue by both researcher and respondents and finding the respondents to participate in the study.

Keywords: knowledge production, dissemination, researchers, challenges, participants, government, information, interviews, population, location

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1. Introduction

Naturally, research is fundamental. It is a challenge or a task that requires in-depth knowledge of the subject matter, planning, care and hard work [1]. A research paper can contribute largely and positively to society, given that the study or the paper provides practical solutions to such communities. Whether one is a student or a doctoral graduate, conducting research is an integral part of being a scholar or practitioner with the necessary skills and credibility to effect social change [2]. There are many upcoming and new researchers, exploring more in research; however, challenges in the process of research persist. These novice researchers may be students from various institutions, interested in starting their careers in academics and have little information about research. New and upcoming researchers encounter challenges when conducting their studies, because they will be trying to grasp the research process. Despite receiving prior training, it remains difficult for them to swiftly comprehend every detail. The process of sharing information and producing knowledge should be accessible and beneficial to society [3].

Higher institutions of learning allow students to explore out of their study in order to provide different knowledge that they may acquire through reading and learning. One person's knowledge may be gained either by experience or education [4]. The body of knowledge is becoming broader. Therefore, it requires people with experience to produce tangible and resourceful knowledge. So,

it is important to allow novel researchers to also gain experience in order to provide the knowledge that can also be used by next generations.

This study highlights challenges, confronting new and upcoming researchers and recommendations, ways of overcoming such challenges in their postgraduate studies. It takes hard work and dedication for new and upcoming researchers to contribute in the body of knowledge. However, upcoming researchers must work industriously to produce new knowledge. This study was conducted by a postgraduate student and supervisor at the University of Limpopo, South Africa, aimed to highlight the challenges, experienced by the new and upcoming researchers when conducting research.

A literature review is crucial for every study in helping recognise the contributions of other scholars on similar topic. [5] Defines literature review is a survey of everything that has been written about a topic, theory, or research question. Literature review is also considered as an integral part of any research study, it provides basis for nature and sources of data to be used, theoretical framework and techniques, used for analysis [6]. The purpose of literature review is to provide an organised overview of existing research on a specific topic, take a critical and evaluative perspective toward published research, summarise, synthesise and analyse the arguments of other authors, uncover similarities and differences or consistencies and inconsistencies within existing research, identify a gap within the body of research and help the researcher to generate and justify his/her research question and hypotheses [7]. When conducting a literature review, a lot can be experienced because this is where now a thorough research needs to be conducted, can be through documentation and through observing.

The purpose of this chapter is to review literature that is related to the challenges, faced by new researchers in all fields of study. Factors, such as allocation of supervisors to new researchers, training of new researchers, can also be considered as factors that can be looked at when it comes to challenges because in order for someone to succeed in research, they need to at least have someone that will be able to guide them through all the phases of research. [8] States that in conducting research, researchers must be cautious, this will also help in terms of knowing what is expected of them in the research field.

With sharing information, which is through research, a specific technique or method should be used to collect data, this is to mean that it will be a challenge that new researchers may face on which method to use, for example; writing qualitative research is a complex activity [9]. Therefore, it will be very important for new and upcoming researcher to be trained on the types of methods to use when conducting research. [2016] State that there are many challenges, facing new researchers and not forgetting those of supervision, such as lack of time, family commitments, lack of adequate theory in the areas being researched on.

Doing literature review and finding relevant sources

Literature review is regarded as one of the most important aspects of research because this is where the researcher must explore what other researchers have researched about on the similar topic. Literature review have different purposes depending on the nature of the inquiry, if the purpose is to advance a position about current state of knowledge, then it is “basic literature review”, and if the purpose of the study is to uncover a research problem for further study, then it is “advanced literature review” [10].

New researchers experience few challenges because there are times were specific and direct information is needed but is not available. One must ensure that they read thoroughly and analyse the literature by other scholars. An important aspect to consider is that doing research is different from doing an undergraduate assignment. [10] States that the task of reviewing literature as a first time or experienced researcher can be done to increase skills and knowledge because one must learn and want satisfaction of completing a job well done. The challenge that newest researchers come across is the issue of patience, [10] further mentioned that in order to succeed in research, the problem of not being patient must be avoided.

Aim of research

- To determine the kind of challenges that first time researchers experience when doing research.
- To find out what are the difficulties of collecting data from participants.

Developing a research topic

In every level of study there is an expectation on the scope of work to do, undergraduates' qualifications do not require much research work. However, depending on various institutions of learning, research is needed in order to complete a qualification. A rhetoric question that can be asked is that how an upcoming researcher can come up with a research topic. [11] Point out that many upcoming writers are uncertain about the style a researcher can use. And even worse, what topic to research about? One can usually think that at the research level there are topics that are given to students in order to choose from, but unfortunately that is not the case. Many students are very excited when registering for their honours degree, attending the classes. However, there is always a time where now they are told to come up with research topics, and that is when the researcher will start to think out of the box in order to come up with a topical research issue. There are other issues that need to be taken into consideration, such as the location, variables, and most importantly the topic that is supposed to be investigated about should be of a concern to the public. It is a bit hard for those doing research for the first time because one must consider the field of study that they are in.

In coming and choosing a topic, it is important to choose a topic that will interest you as a researcher and also consider the following aspects: take your time as you come up with a topic, pick a topic that you are curious about and mostly check with other sources of information [11]. It is written in the paper from the [2] that a research topic is the foundation on everything else rests, so it is very crucial to study a topic carefully. A research topic that involves unemployment and poverty is very sensitive because this is where the researcher needs to interact deeply with the participants about their personal experiences and also invest the emotions to the study, therefore it is recommended that when choosing a topic, new researchers should also choose a topic that will inspire them.

Finding participants

Some research papers are straight forward in terms of the topics, so that makes it easier for the researcher to identify the participants in the study. However, sometimes recruiting participants, going through institutions, can be an additional challenge to the researcher [2]. This can be seen through organising people to take part in the focus group discussions because in order to get such people one must ensure that those people are the right participants for the study.

2. Material and Method

The researcher used both documents analysis and observation as well as interviews to gather data for the purpose of this study.

Research design and methodology

Research methodology is defined and understood as the systematic way of solving a problem. The methodology can, at the same time, be understood as a science of studying how a scientific research is conducted [12]. The study used the following research methodology:

Qualitative Research Method

Qualitative research design is an approach for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. The process of research involves emerging questions and procedures, data, typically collected on the participants' setting [13]. The focus in qualitative research is to understand, explain, explore, discover, and clarify situations, feelings, perceptions, attitudes, values, beliefs and experiences of a group of people [8]. Qualitative research pays less attention to research designs and even less to controlling conditions by construction specific designs. It aims more to create an environment, in which the view of participants or the making of social situations can be analysed and understood [14].

Quantitative research allows the researcher to familiarize him/herself with the problem or concept to be studied, and perhaps generate hypotheses to be tested [15]. Special characteristics of qualitative research are that it: uses an inductive form of reasoning: develops concepts, insights and understanding from patterns in the data, uses the emic perspective of enquiry: derives meaning from the participants' perspective, is ideographic: aims to understand the meaning that people attach to everyday life, regards reality as subjective, captures and discovers meaning once the researcher becomes immersed in the data, uses concepts in the form of themes, motifs and categories, seeks to understand phenomena [16–18].

Population

According to [19], population is a group of people or inhabitants the researcher focused on to determine some common characteristics, population consists of the entire set of objects, group of people or any other set of phenomena to acquire new knowledge and information. [14] Explains that in population it may require that decisions to be made about who will be included and who will be omitted, either way the chances are that there will be very large number of people, possibly several depending about the research. [14] further defines population as the mass of individuals, cases, events, to which the statements of the study will refer, and which must be delimited unambiguously beforehand with regards to the research question and the operationalisation. The municipal officials and local people were targeted in this study. Municipal officials included the municipal manager, tourism development officer and a representative from community service.

Sampling

Sampling is defined by [20], as cited in [21], as a subset of a population. It refers to strategies for assuring that you have the right (means allowing generalisation from the sample to the population because the sample is representative of the population) cases in the study. The study used judgemental or purposive sampling, which is a non-probability type of sampling, which is often associated with case study research design and qualitative research. Purposive sampling occurs when a researcher chooses a particular group or place to study because it is known to be of the type that is wanted [14]. In purposive sampling, the judgment or opinion of some experts forms the basis of the sampling methods. It is expected, that these samples would be better as the experts are supposed to know the population [8, 22].

The participants in the study were selected based on their role and responsibilities in local government, their background because it was beneficial for the researcher to get more information if the participants be open about what they experience.

Data collection techniques

The choice of a method in collection of data depends upon the purpose of the study, the resources available and the skills of the researcher. In selecting the method, the socioeconomic-democratic characteristics of the study population play an important role, it is important to know the characteristics, such as the educational level, age structure, ethnic background [8]. The researcher made use of the following techniques to collect data:

Interviews

Interviewing is a commonly used method of collecting information from people [8]. Interviewing involves interaction of at least two people [8]. The interviews that were conducted were semi-structured because this is the type of interview that allowed the researcher to do follow up on some of the questions answered and for clarity. The aim of the interview is to obtain the individual views of interviewees on an issue [14]. Interviews were conducted with the municipal officials.

The purpose of the interview was to determine the role of the municipality in poverty and high rate of unemployment alleviation in the communities and how the people are empowered and to know from the people in the villages how they are affected in by issues, associated with unemployment and poverty.

Study area

The study was conducted within the Blouberg local municipality, which is the Category B municipality that is categorised as the local municipality, consisting of 226 municipalities, Section 155 (1) of the Constitution provides that a Category B Municipality is one, which shares Municipal executive authority in its area with a Category C Municipality within the area, in which it falls. The Blouberg local municipality is situated within the Capricorn District of the Limpopo Province, in the northern part of South Africa, bordering Zimbabwe and Botswana. It is the largest of four municipalities in the Capricorn district, making up almost half of its geographical area. It has about 22 wards and 137 villages, consisting of 172 601 populations. Blouberg is a home to some of the most spectacular rock, climbing in South Africa. It takes its name from the Blouberg (Blue Mountains), a mountain range, located to the west of the western end of the Soutpansberg Mountain Range, north-west of the town of Vivo. The focused study area was within the Blouberg municipality in the two villages, called Ga-Mareisi and Dilaeneng.

3. Results

The researcher had to firstly go through the municipality to get hold of the people to take part in the discussion because of the knowledge they possessed and the role they play at the community level. The believe was that since the study is about municipality and the local people, the researcher was convinced that the municipality will assist in terms of finding the local people because the researcher is not from that village. The plea fell into deaf ears as the researcher had to arrange and find participants, so they can partake in the study. The researcher had to convince the participants, so that they understand how important the interviews was and how their data can help change things in the local municipality.

In finding the participants, the researcher started at the municipality and purposively chose the ones that their duties/work are related to the study, such as the municipal manager, a representative from the community service department and one from the development and tourism department, while at the communities it was the people that are not working and are mostly affected by poverty. Finding and convincing government officials to participate in research is a serious challenge for the upcoming researchers because of the bureaucracy in government, even if participants want to participate in the study, they will find all reasons not to participate because there is a protocol, which must be followed. The bureaucracy in government makes it impossible for the upcoming researchers to make contribution in the body of knowledge and frustrate the researchers. Moreover, it is very tough for the new researchers because when you experience this kind of challenges, say, maybe in the first research project of your postgraduate studies, one might think this is the struggle that he/she will go through in all other postgraduate degrees and give up on knowledge production.

Setting up appointments with participants for data collection

Setting up of appointments in order to collect data can be tiring, especially if one is not familiar with the environment that the research will be conducted at. After a research proposal has been approved, a lot is still to be done, that is literature review, and begin with methodology, by which in this stage one can at least begin to know the places where data is to be collected. When setting an appointment, a lot is involved, such as cost, making endless phone calls. In the study conducted, the researcher found it very challenging in setting and finalising appointment to collect data, for example, the researcher started to make arrangement telephonically for a period of two months. Moreover, the participants/government officials over the phone made commitments that they are willing to partake in this study. The interactions were good and promising, but surprisingly all turned to be false hope because sometimes just talking to someone over the phone is not enough. After some time, the participants started to give excuses and started talking about bureaucracy.

Since the study was conducted at the municipality, the researcher tried to reach out to one of the participants who was a key respondent in the study but got no luck. The key participants in this study played a hard to get game and caused frustrations to the researcher and majority of them were politicians. It was difficult to get hold of them because they are always busy with political work and do not see the importance of knowledge production. The study involved the one on one interviews and focus group discussions, therefore the researcher wished for a communication with local political leaders from two different villages with the hope that they will assist in terms of gathering participants for a focus group discussion. With all that being said, one can say that the challenge is just failing to arrange and getting hold with the leaders, which cost time because these are the people that the assumption was through talking to them will make things easier when setting appointments. However, with the challenge that was encountered, that did not stop the researcher from planning because the very same week the researcher started to call the municipality in order to make arrangement to meet with the municipal officials as they were part of the sampled size.

From then, it was all about setting appointments with the municipality and it has been tough because you have to call the municipality's office, more specifically the municipal manager's office, to make arrangements, but was told that in order to conduct interviews has to be through the skills development office/section to make all the necessary appointments. Nevertheless, with the hope that all appointments can be set, the person responsible in the skills development department was on leave for weeks, no one was delegated to continue with the responsibilities. In other words, the section was not functioning because the manager was on leave, no services could be provided in

the absence of the manager. This caused a setback for the researcher. As a first-time researcher, one thing to adopt is to be patient at all cost. All sort of communication was done, but still there were challenges at all levels; for example, an email was sent to the municipality, but was told that there is no network to access internet, and this is public organisations, which need internet to function. Yet, clarity was given that an email, requesting an approval to do research at the municipality, has to be sent to the person responsible for skills development who was expected to be back from leave. That is when the researcher had to decide to go to the municipality to finalise all the arrangements and by that time the supervisor is waiting for me (researcher) to bring data, so I can start with transcription. It took the researcher more than two months to set up appointments with government officials to conduct interviews, something that could be done in one day. This caused more frustrations to the researcher who is just a postgraduate student who wanted to complete the qualification and make contribution to the body of knowledge.

Location of interviews

The location of the study is usually determined by the research topic. Finding the exact location to conduct the interviews can be very challenging because one can be able to identify the participants but not have the location to interview such participants. In the study that was conducted, the location of study was at a village, which the researcher was not familiar with. However, it was easier to interview the municipal officials because the location was the municipality's offices. While on the other hand with the focus group discussions and one on one interview with other participants, it was challenging to find the exact location hence there were two focus group discussions to take place. None of the participants wanted to use their home as the location. I had to ask the local traditional leadership for a place to conduct the focus group discussion and one on one interviews and for the other group I had to request one of the local shop and sit under the tree where there is no noise or anything that can distract us to conduct the interviews. The study required a place that participants would sit down and be able to respond to questions, asked by the researcher.

It is very difficult to conduct a study outside and under the tree because the participants easily lose focus and start to concentrate on other things, happening outside. At some stage, the participants instead of answering the questions, asked by the researcher, were looking at some people on the street and all of sudden they started giving examples by the people who were walking on the road in trying to show how unemployment rate affect the community around. At first, the researcher did not see how relevant was that, but after the interviews the researcher realised why it was important for the participants to mention or give examples of the people who were walking on the street

Conducting focus group discussion for the first time

For the researcher to collect data from a group of people, it is important for one to know where and how to gather them. Conducting focus group discussions is a bit challenging for first time researchers because this is the type of interview that is in the form of a group. According to [23], focus group discussions are defined as a rapid assessment, semi-structured method, in which a purposively selected set of participants gather to discuss issues and concerns based on a list of key themes, drawn up by the researcher.

However, having to go through pilot study first before the actual interviews helps a lot because that's where you get the idea of how the discussion will be like. Gathering people was very challenging on its own as the researcher was not familiar with the villagers where Focus Group Discussions was supposed to be conducted. The researcher did not know where to start because one of the leaders of the local structures who offered to help in gathering the community decided to drop the researcher in the 11th hours. The location was known because before coming up with a research topic one must identify the location that is affected. Seeing the people for the first time, making phone calls to meet with the participants of the focus group was tough.

However, at first during the FGDs, the researcher was a bit nervous because most of the people were older and some were asking if whether the research that is conducted will make a difference in their lives or not. When you are new in the field of research and many people are gathered to listen to you as you facilitate the discussion, it is not easy at all. After asking a question and expecting a response from the participants, even after reading the rules of the discussion

and mentioning that one participant at a time, some would start an argument, while you are busy facilitating. I got so frustrated and had to tell them politely that can we have one person at a time. Participants just looked at me and started to undermine me because I am young and being new in the field, I found it difficult to control the group, but I had to keep reminding them of the rules of focus group discussion. Controlling a group of people under the tree is hard, and to make them focus difficult because they will even look at moving cars or anything that can get their attention because you are sitting outside.

Duration of data collection

The duration of data collection usually depends on the type of research methods used, because if two or mixed methods are used, then the duration of data will be long. The study that was conducted did not take long duration. The first step before collection of data is making necessary arrangements and appointments; it took couple of days to collect data, which is fair because it was only qualitative technique that was used in the study. There was the use of tape recorder during data collection, which made things easier because a lot is recorded and less noted down on a notepad. The first day of data collection was at the municipality, which took long hours. There is always estimated interview duration, but that is not guaranteed depending on the discussion in the interview, well that was the case when collecting data, there was an estimated duration, which was forty minutes per interview, but due to long discussions it was more than the estimated time and also a long day for the researcher.

Choosing research methodology

The choice of a research method in research go hand in hand with collection of data because they all depend upon the purpose of the study, the resources available and the skills of the researcher. In selecting the method, the socioeconomic-democratic characteristics of the study population play an important role, it is important to know the characteristics, such as the educational level, age structure, ethnic background [8]. It will be very beneficial for new researchers to know the type of research technique to use, which will make the research easy to conduct. However, the difficulties in choosing the method is when one does not know the relevant method because it is first time research, therefore it is of crucial importance for the upcoming researchers to understand first the types of research methods available before deciding on which one to employ in the research. It took me some time to decide on research method because I had little knowledge of how the method works and why is the research method so important in research. This is where we see the role and importance of the supervisor.

Research fatigue/exhaustion

The early and first stages of research can be tiring because one has to spend lot of time doing documentation research before going to the field to collect data. Even through making the appointments it can also be exhausting because some of the appointments need to be done in person. Meaning one will have to take about four taxis to go to the place and another four coming back. During the time of data collection, preparations, such as printing out consent forms, demographic forms and so on, may lead to a situation where one loses important belongings. On the first day of data collection, which was at the municipality with the officials, the commencement time was in the morning and everything wrapped at the municipality at around late in the afternoon. It was an exhausting day, but also worth it at the same time, and because it was late already, I had to go and rest. Weariness can compromise the data collected.

After the interviews, because of fatigue, it was not easy to transcribe the voice records though I understood the importance of transcribing after the interviews because that helps one not to forget what was discussed during the day and compare the data with the notes. The researcher spends most of the time standing and talking under the sun, after the interviews all that is needed is to rest. When the mind is exhausted, even the body language changes and the responded will not take you seriously if they realised that you are tired.

Sensitive information from participants

When it comes to providing information, often it becomes difficult for people to just open up and talk about their lives. A topic, such as “*The impact of high unemployment on poverty*” requires deep engagement, so in terms of having to gather specific and sensitive information is

challenging. When it comes to asking some questions, such as “why is the municipality failing to help the people” to the municipal officials, their facial expressions would tell that the question that was asked was very sensitive, especially considering that they are the people that the public is trusting, and a municipality is an institution that is close to the people and must provide satisfaction to their needs. The officials would rather respond that he/she doesn't know, but you could see that the respondent knows is just that he/she does not want to reveal more information. While on the other hand with community members, any question that has to do with unemployment and poverty was very sensitive to them because these are the people that are always complaining that the municipality or rather the government is not doing enough to provide them with basic necessities and job opportunities.

Most of the participants were not open at first and not comfortable discussing their personal experiences even after promising them that what we discussed in the interviews remain there and no one is supposed to share with anyone outside or after the interviews.

Government officials withheld the important information, which will help the researchers to come up with solutions to the problems because they are afraid that if they give more and sensitive information that might put their jobs at risk. The officials rather tell lies for you not to keep asking questions, which will put them in danger. At some point, some of the officials will keep postponing the interview dates for you to give up or just give excuse after excuse to try to show you that they don't want to participate in the study. When collecting biographical information, it was also hard especially in the focus group discussions; people were not free to share their age and educational background. Because they are from one community, some do not feel comfortable with other members knowing their age. In a situation where the participants are not educated, there are possibilities that the participants may not tell the truth about their educational background. However, the researcher had to talk to the participants in private in order to gather information about the participants' age and educational background.

Some would argue that it is not easy to just reveal everything about the municipality because you do not know who is listening, you will ever know what is to happen after the discussion, and some might take the information to the local leaders.

Lack of resources

First time researchers should know that resources are very important in any research undertaken because without resources it will be difficult for the researcher to achieve their goals. You will need transport to and from the field to collect raw data more especially if you are engaged in empirical study, which is more important in generating new knowledge or contributing to the knowledge production. At the field, the researcher needs some refreshments to cool up more especially under the scorching sun of South Africa. The upcoming researchers will need stationery, especially when doing surveys, you will need to print out the survey instruments for data collection, interview guide for qualitative data collection as well as voice recorder, laptop, access to internet and phone. Lack of resources can also mean not having enough material to just do a literature review and this will result in plagiarism, which is an offence in the field of science.

4. Discussion

The study shows that it is very difficult for the emerging researchers to engage in the research process for the first time. There are so many challenges, that the upcoming researchers experience, starting with drafting their research topic. The researchers need to identify the problem first before thinking about how to develop the research topic. Some of the emerging researchers find this to be a very difficult task because they have to do some review of literature, which is problematic sometimes because of shortage of resources. Review of literature is very crucial in the sense that it helps a researcher to see the findings of the previous researchers who wrote about the same subjects. However, there is still a problem of identifying and arranging for the interviews with the participants. Some participants withhold the information, which they claim to be a sensitive information, which they could not divulge. This is so frustrating because they withhold the information that the researchers need to be able to make contribution into the body of knowledge. When arranging for the interviews, especially with the public officials in senior positions, it becomes a

challenges that emerging researchers go through, it's either the officials do not have time to do interviews or they are having a busy schedule. The emerging researchers have never done a focus group discussion before and when they do it in their studies, they feel so threatened and find it difficult to control the participants in the group discussion. None the less, failure to control the participants in your discussion will result in a mess because participants will just talk at the same time. Therefore, the researchers must outline the focus group discussion rules before starting with the discussion, so that each and every participant understands the rules for a smooth and proper group discussion.

The stress and everything that the emerging researchers experience may lead to fatigue. The body and mind will be affected in such a way that the researcher would feel frustrated and might want to give up on the important study. Location of interviews also plays a critical role, interviews must be conducted in a very quiet place in the absence of noise or any form of distraction.

The recommendations with regard to the challenges, faced by the new upcoming researchers, are those of ensuring that the new researcher is given proper training and classes on how to choose a topic, hence such topic should be the one that the researcher can enjoy, the topic that is doable, and this can be done through ensuring that a rightful and professional supervisor is allocated to the new researcher. None the less, it is critically important, that the supervisor must be a specialist in that field. In terms of data collection, being the interviews, a pilot study should be conducted. And while on the other hand finding participants can be stressful, it is advisable that one should not stop at first rejection [2]. [8] Recommend that there must be provision of conference papers both at local and international conferences because it is in such conferences that new and upcoming researchers can polish their investigations. The recommendation that can be given to new upcoming researchers is to ensure that when they conduct their studies, it has to be places where is not far to avoid transport costs. And do a study that is does not require lots of money and costs.

Study Limitation. The study had potential limitations because of its nature. Government officials are difficult to find when you want them to partake in the study and they will always give excuses like having a busy schedule all the time. Setting up interviews was a bit of challenges because the interviews had to be conducted in the offices of the respondents in a busy environment where there is too much distraction from colleagues. It was not easy to set up interviews with the senior government officials, so the researchers had to go to the facilities on busy days when the key respondents are available

This strategy was so effective in such a way that the required data was gathered on the day. Officials confirmed their availability on the day of the interviews and they participated in the study. This was after a very lengthy process of going to the offices and request for appointments.

Recommendation for Future research. The authors recommended the following for future research:

- bureaucracy in the public sector and the role of senior officials in relation to knowledge production;
- the challenges that researchers experience when conducting research, especially with senior officials in government;
- the attitude of senior government officials towards research.

5. Conclusion

This research paper discussed the challenges, faced by new and upcoming researchers, and also provided some of the recommendations that can be applied by upcoming researchers in any field of study. The upcoming researchers always find it difficult having to deal with different participants and this makes it difficult for them to participate in knowledge production. However, it is important, that public officials participate in this kind of evidence gathering, and this will assist them in making informed decisions to better improve in their different departments. It is very important, that the community members are taught about research and the importance of research in their daily lives. Majority of government officials sometimes are not willing to participate in research undertaken because of bureaucracy in their different organisations and this makes it hard for the upcoming researchers to collect raw data when engaging in linguistic data. The more the participants make it hard for the researchers when wanting to collect data, the more this breaks their confidence and may discourage them from participating in any research in future.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] Qasem, F. (2019). The challenges and problems faced by students in the early stage of writing research projects in L2, University of Bisha. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331354228_THE_CHALLENGES_AND_PROBLEMS_FACED_BY_STUDENTS_IN_THE_EARLY_STAGE_OF_WRITING_RESEARCH_PROJECTS_IN_L2_UNIVERSITY_OF_BISHA_SAUDI_ARABIA
- [2] Research Challenges (And how to overcome them) (2010). Walden Magazine. Available at: <https://www.waldenu.edu/news-and-events/publications/articles/2010/01-research-challenges>
- [3] Biamah, E. K., Kogo, B. (2013). Developments in Earth Surface Processes. Kenya: A Natural Outlook.
- [4] Carayannis, E. G., Campbell, D. F. J. (2018). Definition of Key Terms: Knowledge, Knowledge Production, Innovation, Democracy, and Governance. SpringerBriefs in Business, 5–15. doi: http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-01517-6_2
- [5] Skene, A. (2019) The Writing Centre. University of Toronto at Scarborough.
- [6] Ahmad, Z. A., Jangraiz, K. (2016). An analysis of the causes and Consequences of Unemployment in District Peshawar. JOSSH, 1 (1), 115–127.
- [7] Tancezer, L. M. (2015). Literature Review, Learning Development Service. Queen's University Belfast. Available at: <https://www.qub.ac.uk/graduate-school/Filestore/Fileupload,597676,en.pdf>
- [8] Kumar, R. (2014). Research Methodology: A Step-by-Step Guide for Beginners. London: SAGE Publications, 440.
- [9] Wang, F. (2013). Challenges of Learning to Write Qualitative Research: Students' Voices. International Journal of Qualitative Methods, 12 (1), 638–651. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1177/160940691301200134>
- [10] Machi, L. A., McEvoy, B. T. (2009). The Literature Review. California: Corwin Press.
- [11] Winkler, A. C., McCuen, J. R. (1989). Writing the Research Paper, Harcourt Brace Jovanovich Publishers. London, 381.
- [12] Malatji, T. L. (2017). Challenges in the Implementation of Proactive Land Acquisition Strategy (PLAS) in Mopani District area. Limpopo Province, 87.
- [13] Creswell, J. W. (2009). Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches. SAGE, 270.
- [14] Flick, U. (2015). Qualitative data analysis. Development, trends, challenges. Qualitative inquiry and the politics of research. Walnut Creek: Left Coast Press
- [15] Golafshani, N. (2003). Understanding reliability and validity in qualitative research. The qualitative report, 8 (4), 597–607. doi: <http://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2003.1870>
- [16] Brink, P. J., Wood, M. J. (1998). Advanced design in nursing research. Sage. doi: <http://doi.org/10.4135/9781452204840>
- [17] Bocar, A., (2013). Difficulties Encountered by the Student-Researchers and the Effects on Their Research Output. doi: <http://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1612050>
- [18] Barnes, R. W., Grove, J. W., Burns, N. H. (2003) Experimental assessment of factors affecting transfer length. Structural Journal, 100 (6), 740–748. doi: <http://doi.org/10.14359/12840>
- [19] Selolo, R. E. (2018). Factors influencing parent involvement in the education of their children at primary school level in Bahananwa Circuit in Blouberg Municipality. Limpopo Province.
- [20] Salkind, N. J. (2006). Encyclopaedia of measurement and statistics. SAGE publications.
- [21] Rakgwale, S. M. (2010). Impact of inadequate conflict management skills on service delivery at Modipe High school in Limpopo Province. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10386/570>
- [22] Mapolisa, T. (2012). Challenges being experienced by undergraduate students in conducting research in open and distance learning. International Journal of Asian Social Science, 2 (10), 1672–1684. doi: <http://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v10i2.593>
- [23] Escalada, M., Heong, K. L. (2014). Focus Group Discussion. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242589494>

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